

INTEGRATING SUSTAINABILITY AND HEALTH IN BUILDINGS THROUGH RENEWABLE MATERIALS

INNORENEW CoE INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE
2020

INNORENEW CoE

Livade 6, 6310 Izola, Slovenia

IRIC2020 SCIENTIFIC COMMITTEE

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WELCOME

As we open the second InnoRenew CoE International Conference, it's hard not to think of all that has changed in the year and a half that has passed since our debut conference.

Although the pandemic has dramatically changed our day-to-day lives, it has not changed society's need to address the rapidly changing climate, reconsider our economic priorities, and refocus our attention on important social issues. Buildings remain part of the solution to many problems, and I think it is becoming clear that we need to consider much more about buildings than the basics of shelter.

As the pandemic kept us indoors, many of us may have realised that our indoor environment plays an even more important role in our well-being and happiness than we previously acknowledged. Likewise, we may have considered more carefully how buildings affect the well-being of those who live in different circumstances. Access to safe, comfortable, and healthy living and working spaces is (and should be) a priority in a just society.

Another major change that will affect our work in the years to come is the introduction of the European Green Deal, which will be a major driver of sustainable development in Europe. The European Green Deal prioritises investment and innovation in building renovation solutions for energy performance and attempts to ensure these solutions reach all members of society. The European Green Deal recognizes the need to establish high-performance housing for all and will support renovation in social housing, schools, and other facilities that are often left behind. This is a step in the right direction for inclusive, high-performing buildings.

I rarely find proclamations of success convincing when it comes to sustainability – especially about buildings. We must continue to drive change through research, development, and innovation to make our built environment a beacon of sustainable development. We cannot be satisfied with the environmental performance of our products or buildings; we cannot allow people to be excluded from our advancements; and we cannot forget that buildings impact the well-being and happiness of their occupants.

At this year's InnoRenew CoE International Conference, we wanted to showcase how renewable materials play an integral role in sustainable construction by highlighting environmental performance, safety, and health as well as the economic, digital, and social links that bind us to the materials in the built environment. Conference presenters will discuss advances in design, material development, health research, retrofitting, environmental assessment, and many other topics that increase the efficiency and performance of the building and renewable materials sectors.

Carlo Battisti, President of Living Future Europe, will weave together these complementary threads in his keynote address, "Healthy, living transparent. The quiet revolution of materials". He works to push for change and supports researchers, architects, engineers, and other construction professionals to achieve it. His efforts have expanded knowledge and acceptance of restorative sustainability and regenerative design within Europe's construction community. We are excited and grateful for his participation in our conference.

Together, the contributions paint a hopeful picture. But we must continue to push the science forward, embed these innovations in normal construction practices, and ensure inclusion of all who can benefit from our hard work.

While I wish these matters could have been discussed in person in Izola, we must embrace new options for discourse on these topics. I hope the conference inspires you to reach out to one another and continue sharing, collaborating, and building communities that embrace the challenge of creating a sustainable and just built environment. You may also consider our new open access and peer-reviewed journal, *Interdisciplinary Perspectives on the Built Environment*, as a place to share the insights your work provides.

Thank you,

Dr Michael Burnard
Deputy Director, InnoRenew CoE
Assist. Prof., University of Primorska

SCHEDULE AT A GLANCE

MORNING

WELCOME
9:00–9:05

KEYNOTE
9:05–9:35

FLASH TALKS
9:35–10:35

COFFEE BREAK
10:35–11:00

**HUMAN HEALTH IN THE
BUILT ENVIRONMENT**
11:00–12:30

LUNCH
12:30–14:00

AFTERNOON

COMPLEMENTARY TOPICS
14:00–15:30

COFFEE BREAK
15:30–15:55

**SUSTAINABLE CONSTRUCTION
WITH RENEWABLE MATERIALS**
15:55–17:25

CLOSING
17:25–17:30

KEYNOTE ADDRESS

CARLO BATTISTI
PRESIDENT, LIVING FUTURE EUROPE

*Healthy, living, transparent.
The quiet revolution of materials.*

Carlo Battisti has a degree in civil engineering from the Politecnico of Milan, nearly twenty years of experience in construction companies and a master's in management and organizational development from MIP International Business School. His certifications include Certified Project Manager IPMA®; LEED®, Living Future and WELL Accredited Professional; GBC Home AP, GBC Historic Building AP; USGBC® and WELL Faculty™.

Since 2009, he has been working with IDM South Tyrol (Italy) as an innovation manager in the Business Development department, Construction. From 2010 to 2011, he worked with the Energy and Environment Cluster of Trentino as manager of the business unit for sustainable products. From 2015 to 2016, he was the co-owner of a startup focused on LEED consulting. In 2015, he co-founded the Living Future Italy Collaborative.

Since 2017, he has been working with Eurac Research as Chair and Project Manager of COST Action 16114 RESTORE (REthinking Sustainability TOwards a Regenerative Economy). The RESTORE COST Action (2017–2021) will affect a paradigm shift towards restorative sustainability for new and existing buildings and space design across Europe through the collaboration of 160+ researchers from 40 European countries.

Since 2018, he is European Executive Director for the International Living Future Institute and current President of Living Future Europe. The Institute's mission will hasten the change and provide needed direction towards a regenerative design transition in Europe. It is actively pursuing European market alignment and adaptations of the Living Building Challenge (LBC).

AGENDA

WELCOME | 9:00-9:05

Dr Michael Burnard, InnoRenew CoE

KEYNOTE | 9:05-9:35

Carlo Battisti, Living Future Europe

FLASH TALKS | 9:35-10:35

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*Unable to present

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CLOSING | 17:25-17:30

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Flash Talks

Molecular Dynamics Investigation of Capturing Paracrystalline Cellulose Phase from Mixed Crystalline and Amorphous Cellulose Under Constant Load

Veerapandian Ponnuchamy¹, Jakub Sandak^{1,2}, Anna Sandak^{1,3}

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² University of Primorska, Andrej Marušič Institute

³ University of Primorska, Faculty of Mathematics, Natural Sciences and Information Technologies

Cellulose is one of the major abundant biopolymers on earth, roughly half of all plants are constituted from it. It is composed of linearly dispersed glucose polymers that are strongly bonded through hydrogen bonds. Two distinct phases of cellulose can be seen in a typical wood, namely crystalline and amorphous region. The ratio of crystalline and amorphous region controls the typical properties such as rigidity and flexibility of the cellulose fibers. The mechanical properties of the cellulose depend on the amount of crystallinity and organization of both phases. Moreover, combined crystalline and amorphous have not been analyzed in detail and no systematic study exists on the investigation of paracrystalline phase formation under constant load conditions. The investigation of paracrystalline's structural morphology, hydrogen bond information and mechanical properties are thus necessary for understanding microfibril at molecular level. To address these issues, we employ molecular dynamics simulations to study of the formation of paracrystalline states under constant load. GROMACS was used for all MD simulations with GROMOS 53a6 force field. The system is composed of a mixture of crystalline cellulose plates and amorphous cellulose. Each crystalline cellulose plate is comprised of 30 glucose chains, with each chain containing 18 glucose units and each amorphous contains four glucose chains with 518 units. The amorphous region is confined between two plates. The upper crystalline plate is fixed, and the bottom plate is loading with different forces, for instance, 1000, 3000, 5000, 7000 kJ mol⁻¹ nm⁻². The radial distribution function (RDF) demonstrates that the obtained long range ordering for paracrystalline lies between that of corresponding amorphous and crystalline peaks (Kulasinski et al., 2014). The RDF peak intensity increases at increasing load. Therefore, paracrystalline state is predominant and also inevitable at the crystal and amorphous interphase.

Keywords: molecular dynamics, cellulose, paracrystalline state, constant load, amorphous

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REFERENCE

Kulasinski, K., Keten, S., Churakov, S.V., Derome, D., Carmeliet J., 2014. A comparative molecular dynamics study of crystalline, paracrystalline and amorphous states of cellulose. *Cellulose*. 21(3), 1103-16. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s10570-014-0213-7>

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